

1 **A Lightweight, Flexible and Mechanically Robust Nonwoven Copper Metallized Nylon-6**
2 **Fibers for Enhanced Charge Dissipation and Reduced Electrical Resistance for ESD**
3 **Protection**

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21

22 **Abstract**

23 Electrostatic discharges pose significant risks in electronics, aerospace and healthcare
24 sectors, where uncontrolled static charges can damage devices or cause hazardous events.
25 Advanced protective textiles must balance electrostatic protection with mechanical strength and

26 breathability. Here we present Nylon-6 (PA6) fibers coated with Cu using physical vapor
27 deposition to suppress static charge buildup while maintaining structural integrity. Using a
28 combination of structural, chemical and mechanical analyses, we show that Cu-coated fibers
29 reduce triboelectric activity, improve mechanical performance, and retain breathability and
30 moisture permeability suitable for wearable applications. Surface analysis revealed the presence
31 of copper oxide, which forms during the coating process and contributes to the observed
32 properties. These findings demonstrate that metalized fibers offer a promising strategy for next-
33 generation protective textiles, combining durability, comfort and effective electrostatic
34 discharge control for use in sensitive environments.

35 **1. Introduction**

36 Electrostatic Discharge (ESD) protection is essential across various industries, including
37 electronics manufacturing, aerospace, automotive, medical, and defense.^[1] ESD is the sudden
38 flow of electricity between two electrically charged objects, which can damage sensitive
39 electronic components and disrupt device functionality.^[2] The risks it poses to delicate
40 electronics are well-documented, often leading to malfunctions or failures. The demand for
41 effective safeguards has intensified as devices become increasingly compact and fragile.
42 Beyond electronics, controlling ESD is also critical in environments handling flammable
43 materials, where uncontrolled discharges can trigger hazardous incidents.^[3] A material's ability
44 to generate and retain static charges depends on its position in the triboelectric series,
45 influencing susceptibility to ESD events; this behavior can be further tuned by nanoparticle
46 additives or surface treatments to make materials more or less triboelectrically active.^[4-8]
47 Effective ESD protection requires materials with surface resistance in the dissipative range,
48 ensuring rapid charge decay while minimizing triboelectric charging.^[9] Various ESD-protective
49 materials have been developed to achieve this, including packaging and textiles designed to
50 manage static charges.^[2,10,11] Protective packaging shields electronic components during

51 transport and storage by balancing charge dissipation with environmental control.^[12–14] In
52 workplaces such as electronics production, cleanrooms, hospitals, and laboratories, antistatic
53 textiles—including uniforms, aprons, and wrist or heel straps—are crucial in mitigating ESD
54 risks. These textiles can incorporate conductive fillers, conductive fibers, or metallization to
55 effectively dissipate charges and prevent discharges during handling. Additionally, breathable
56 ESD-protective textiles are essential to ensure comfort, particularly in environments requiring
57 prolonged wear.^[15,16] Preventing ESD reduces material waste and rework expenses. Many
58 industries, especially electronics and aerospace, enforce strict ESD standards. Non-compliance
59 can result in legal penalties and loss of certification. By reducing failures, improving reliability,
60 and cutting down on unnecessary costs, businesses can enhance productivity and maintain a
61 competitive edge in the market.^[17]

62 However, many existing approaches to ESD protection suffer from limitations that
63 hinder their suitability for wearable applications.^[18] Conductive fillers such as carbon black or
64 the incorporation of wires from stainless steel can compromise flexibility or wearing
65 comfort.^[19] Conductive inks and intrinsically conductive polymers, while initially effective,
66 tend to exhibit poor long-term durability, particularly under washing or mechanical stress.^[20]
67 Moreover, hybrid fiber architectures such as core–sheath or bicomponent designs, though
68 promising in terms of tailored conductivity, typically require complex fabrication processes and
69 are associated with high production costs, which limits their scalability and widespread
70 adoption.^[18] These persistent trade-offs highlight the need for new materials and processing
71 strategies that simultaneously offer high conductivity, comfort, mechanical resilience, and
72 manufacturability.^[18]

73 Electrospinning has emerged as a powerful technique for producing ultrafine fibrous
74 non-wovens that are highly porous, lightweight, and mechanically robust.^[21] This versatile
75 method enables the fabrication of continuous polymer fibers with diameters ranging from the

76 microscale to the nanometer scale, offering high surface area-to-volume ratios and tunable
77 structural properties.^[22] Such characteristics make electrospun materials highly attractive for
78 multifunctional applications, including filtration, biomedical scaffolds, energy harvesting, and
79 wearable electronics.^[23–26]

80 In the context of ESD protection, electrospun fibers provide an ideal platform for surface
81 modifications and conductive coatings, creating breathable, flexible, and efficient charge-
82 dissipative materials without compromising comfort or performance. Physical Vapor
83 Deposition (PVD) is a widely used technique for coating materials with thin metallic films,
84 offering precise control over thickness, composition, and surface properties.^[27] Metals such as
85 Cu are particularly advantageous in ESD protection due to their high electrical conductivity.
86 This enables rapid charge dissipation and minimizes triboelectric charging.^[28] By integrating
87 Cu coatings onto polymeric substrates, PVD can enhance the conductivity and durability of
88 electrospun fiber meshes, creating lightweight and breathable materials suitable for wearable
89 protective applications in sensitive environments.

90 In this work, we present the development of metalized fibers based on nylon-6 (PA6), a
91 polymer widely used in the textile industry due to its mechanical strength and versatility. By
92 coating PA6 fibers with Cu using a PVD method, we aim to reduce the fibers' tendency to
93 accumulate triboelectric charges significantly. To comprehensively evaluate the impact of
94 metallization, we applied a range of characterization techniques, including Scanning Electron
95 Microscopy (SEM) for morphology and diameter analysis, Energy-Dispersive X-ray
96 Spectroscopy (EDS) for elemental composition, Attenuated Total Reflectance–Fourier
97 Transform Infrared (ATR-FTIR) spectroscopy to detect Cu–O bonding indicative of copper
98 oxide formation, contact angle measurements to evaluate surface wettability, Water Vapor
99 Transmission Rate (WVTR) testing for breathability, mechanical testing to assess tensile
100 properties, and electrical measurements to determine resistance and triboelectric performance.

101 This multi-technique approach demonstrates the potential of PVD metallization in creating ESD
102 protective components while preserving the desirable physical properties of PA6 fiber non-
103 wovens. A graphical representation of the concept explored in this article is shown in **Figure**
104 **1a**.

105 **2. Results and Discussion**

106 The PA6 meshes were obtained via electrospinning following the previous
107 protocols.^[29,30] We selected PA6 due to their unique surface, mechanical properties and tuned
108 wettability.^[31–33] Next, the effect of the metallization process on the morphology and diameter
109 of PA6 fibers was evaluated using SEM imaging, see **Figure 1b-g**. Commercially available
110 textile was also imaged as a reference point for comparison, see **Figure 1f**. The metallization
111 process gradually increased fiber diameter with deposition times of 450, 600, and 750 s. The
112 pristine PA6 fibers had a mean diameter of 163 ± 15 nm. Following metallization, the fiber
113 diameter increased incrementally to 170 ± 21 nm for PA6_Cu15, 175 ± 20 nm for PA6_Cu20,
114 and 182 ± 20 nm for PA6_Cu25 after the longest metallization time. This increase can be
115 attributed to the deposition of Cu on the fiber surface during the PVD process. Despite the
116 incremental thickening, the fibers retained their morphology, with no observable deformation,
117 such as flattening, cracking, or aggregation, even after prolonged metallization of 750 s. This
118 suggests that the metallization parameters were sufficiently controlled to ensure uniform
119 deposition without compromising the structural characteristics of the PA6 fibers. Such
120 precision highlights the base polymeric material's robustness and the compatibility of the PVD
121 metallization method with nanofibrous substrates.^[34]

122

123 **Figure 1.** Conceptual illustration and morphological characterization of Cu-coated PA6 fibers.

124 (a) Schematic representation of the research concept. (b–e) SEM micrographs depicting the
 125 morphology of pristine PA6 and Cu-coated PA6 fibers with varying Cu deposition times:
 126 PA6_Cu15, PA6_Cu20, and PA6_Cu25. (f) SEM micrographs of a commercial textile used for
 127 reference. (g) Histogram showing the progressive increase in diameter of coated fibers with
 128 increasing Cu deposition time.

129 The elemental composition of PA6 fibers with varying Cu coating thickness was
 130 analyzed using EDS. **Figure 2a–d** illustrates the elemental mapping of C within all samples,
 131 respectively. The presence of a uniform C signal across all samples confirms the purity and
 132 uniformity of the fibers. The Cu-coated samples shown in **Figure 2f–h** exhibit a homogeneous
 133 Cu distribution along the fibers, demonstrating the successful incorporation of Cu on the

134 polymer fibers. On the combined EDS spectra from all samples shown in **Figure 2i**, we can
135 observe characteristic peaks for C, N, O, Cu, and Al. The Cu peak is absent in the pure PA6
136 spectrum but appears in the spectra of Cu-coated samples, with increasing intensity
137 corresponding to thicker Cu coating. The presence of Al in all spectra originates from the
138 substrate (Al stub) used for analysis. The spectra confirm the expected elemental composition
139 of PA6, with prominent peaks for C, N, and O. And it is clear that the intensity of the Cu signal
140 increases with the thickness of Cu coating, confirming a controlled and consistent integration
141 of Cu on the surface of the fibers.

142

143 **Figure 2.** Chemical composition analysis of Cu-coated PA6 fibers using EDS and FTIR. (a–d)

144 Elemental mapping of carbon (C) distribution in pristine PA6, PA6_Cu15, PA6_Cu20, and

145 PA6_Cu25 fibers. (e–h) Elemental mapping of copper (Cu) distribution in the corresponding

146 samples, indicating uniform Cu deposition. (i) EDS spectra showing the presence of C, N, O,

147 Cu, and Al, with increasing Cu peak intensity corresponding to greater deposition thickness. (j)

148 Full FTIR spectra comparing pristine and Cu-coated PA6 fibers. (k) Magnified FTIR spectral

149 region highlighting the Cu–O vibrational peaks, confirming the presence of copper oxide (CuO)
150 on the fiber surface.

151 After EDS, we performed FTIR measurements to further investigate the structure of the
152 fibers, as shown in **Figures 2j** and **2k**. First, we investigated uncoated PA6 fibers, which served
153 as a baseline. Characteristic peaks were observed at 3293 cm⁻¹ (Free N-H axial deformation),
154 3083 cm⁻¹ (N-H angular deformation in the plane), 2931 cm⁻¹ and 2859 cm⁻¹ (aliphatic C-H
155 stretching), 1639 cm⁻¹ (amide I, C=O axial deformation), 1546 cm⁻¹ (amide II, C-N axial
156 deformation and CO-N-H angular deformation), and additional peaks at 1437 cm⁻¹ (γ -phase),
157 1373 cm⁻¹ (CN axial deformation), 1278 cm⁻¹, and 728 cm⁻¹ (angular deformation out of plane,
158 CH₂), consistent with the typical vibrational modes of PA6. Our results are consistent with the
159 literature, as reported by Guerrini et al.^[35] Upon deposition of Cu coatings on the PA6 fibers,
160 distinct peaks at 530 cm⁻¹ and 580 cm⁻¹ corresponding to Cu-O vibrational modes became
161 visible, see **Figure 2k**.^[36] These peaks are attributed to copper oxide (CuO) on the coated fibers.
162 The CuO is likely formed during the PVD process as highly reactive Cu readily oxidizes under
163 room conditions when exposed to ambient air.^[37] This oxidation leads to the formation of CuO,
164 which was subsequently detected on the fibers through FTIR analysis. Notably, the intensity of
165 these Cu-O peaks increased with increasing Cu coating thickness (PA6_Cu15, PA6_Cu20, and
166 PA6_Cu25). The combined findings from EDS and FTIR analyses confirm the successful
167 deposition of Cu onto PA6 fibers while preserving the polymer's structural integrity. The
168 presence of CuO, indicated by both Cu–O vibrational peaks in FTIR and elemental detection in
169 EDS, suggests that oxidation occurs after the metallized fibers are exposed to the atmosphere.
170 Our findings are also in line with a previous report showing with XPS that copper films
171 deposited by PVD undergo spontaneous surface oxidation under ambient conditions, leading to
172 the formation of Cu²⁺ species such as CuO and Cu(OH)₂.^[38]

173 After morphology and elemental analysis, the wetting properties of the prepared
174 materials were also investigated. Metallization notably influenced the wetting properties of the
175 fibers, see **Figure 3a**. The uncoated PA6 fibers exhibited a hydrophilic contact angle of $54 \pm$
176 2° . This angle progressively decreased as the thickness of the Cu coating increased.
177 Specifically, the contact angles were measured as $55 \pm 4^\circ$ for PA6_Cu15, $41 \pm 5^\circ$ for
178 PA6_Cu20, and $33 \pm 4^\circ$ for PA6_Cu25. The contact angle decreased with increasing Cu coating
179 thickness, indicating enhanced hydrophilicity of the fiber surface. This behavior is attributed to
180 the formation of copper oxide species upon ambient exposure, which are hydrophilic.^[39] For
181 comparison, a commercial textile sample was tested, which displayed complete wetting,
182 corresponding to a contact angle of 0° . The contact angle results of PA6 fibers align with the
183 literature, showing that PA6 was hydrophilic.^[40]

184 Similarly to our findings, Hashmi et al. observed enhanced hydrophilicity in CuO-
185 loaded polyacrylonitrile (PAN) fibers.^[41] Their study demonstrated that increasing the
186 concentration of CuO nanoparticles reduced the contact angle from 124° for pristine PAN to 0°
187 for PAN containing 1% CuO nanoparticles.^[41] Therefore, we show that similar results can be
188 achieved via metallization.

189

190 **Figure 3.** Wettability, breathability, and mechanical properties of Cu-coated PA6 fibers. (a)
 191 Contact angle measurements demonstrating the effect of Cu metallization on hydrophilicity,
 192 with corresponding droplet images for each sample. White scale bars represent 1mm. (b)
 193 WVTR measurements, indicating the impact of Cu deposition on breathability. (c)
 194 Representative stress-strain curves of pristine and Cu-coated PA6 fiber meshes. (d) Comparison
 195 of maximum stress and toughness for each sample type, illustrating the mechanical
 196 reinforcement provided by Cu coating.

197 The impact of Cu coating on the WVTR of electrospun PA6 fibers was evaluated to
198 assess breathability. As shown in **Figure 3b**, uncoated PA6 fibers exhibited the highest WVTR
199 ($4.84 \pm 0.05 \text{ kgm}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$), indicating excellent moisture permeability. With increasing Cu
200 thickness, a gradual reduction in WVTR was observed, with PA6_Cu15 and PA6_Cu20
201 showing slightly lower values. PA6_Cu25 exhibited the most significant decrease, reaching
202 $3.85 \pm 0.28 \text{ kgm}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$. However, the WVTR remained within the range of highly breathable
203 materials, even at its lowest. For comparison, wool, which is considered highly breathable, has
204 been reported to exhibit a WVTR of $1.3 \text{ kgm}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$, meaning that even the least breathable
205 Cu-coated PA6 sample retains at least 3 times higher permeability.^[42] This slight reduction in
206 WVTR suggests that while Cu deposition enhances the fiber's moisture barrier properties, it
207 does not significantly compromise breathability. As a result, these materials remain suitable for
208 applications requiring electrostatic protection and comfort and are in the same range as the
209 commercial reference material, which exhibited the WVTR of $4.39 \pm 0.15 \text{ kgm}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$,
210 showing the suitability of obtained non-wovens for clothing.^[43–45]

211 To further investigate the origin of the breathability differences observed in WVTR
212 tests, we conducted image-based analysis of SEM micrographs to estimate the average pore
213 area across pristine and Cu-coated PA6 meshes. The results (**Figure S1**, Supporting
214 Information) reveal that the mean pore area remains consistent across all samples, indicating
215 that the global porosity and fibrous architecture are not significantly affected by Cu coating. As
216 such, the moderate reduction in WVTR values with increasing Cu thickness is likely governed
217 by the surface wetting behavior rather than structural changes. This is supported by contact
218 angle measurements (**Figure 3a**), which show an increase in hydrophilicity with thicker Cu
219 coatings, promoting faster water uptake and possibly altering moisture retention dynamics
220 during WVTR testing.

221 Next, the mechanical properties of metallized PA6 were evaluated, as shown in **Figure**
222 **3c-d**. The deposition of Cu resulted in significant performance enhancements in PA6 fibers.
223 The pure PA6 sample exhibited a maximum stress of 3.81 ± 0.27 MPa. Incorporating Cu at
224 different thicknesses led to a progressive enhancement in mechanical strength. PA6_Cu15
225 exhibited a 33.9% increase, reaching 5.10 ± 1.97 MPa, while PA6_Cu20 displayed an 80.8 %
226 improvement with a maximum stress of 6.89 ± 0.73 MPa. The highest recorded value was for
227 PA6_Cu25, achieving 7.12 ± 0.18 MPa, corresponding to an 86.9 % increase over unmodified
228 PA6. In addition to improving maximum stress, the toughness of the PA6 composites increased
229 substantially with Cu metallization. The pure PA6 sample exhibited a toughness of $0.163 \pm$
230 0.021 MJm⁻³. Metallized samples demonstrated a progressive enhancement, with PA6_Cu15
231 achieving a 15.8% increase (0.22 ± 0.082 MJm⁻³), PA6_Cu20 reaching 64.2% higher toughness
232 (0.312 ± 0.069 MJm⁻³), and PA6_Cu25 exhibiting the highest recorded toughness at 82.6%
233 improvement (0.347 ± 0.042 MJm⁻³). The increase in toughness suggests that Cu metallization
234 enhances the energy absorption capability of PA6 under mechanical loading, potentially due to
235 improved interfacial adhesion and load distribution of the polymer-metal nanocomposite. The
236 trend of diminishing returns observed for both maximum stress and toughness at higher Cu
237 concentrations aligns with a possible saturation effect, where additional metallization no longer
238 significantly enhances mechanical properties. These findings provide insight into optimizing
239 Cu metallization thickness for mechanical reinforcement of PA6-based composites. Our results
240 are in line with the literature, as similar behavior was shown by Kim et al. on polyurethane
241 fibers where tensile strength and elongation at break increased with the thickness of Cu
242 coating.^[46] The increase in mechanical properties can be explained by forming a polymer-metal
243 nanocomposite layer in the interface areas of organic fibers and metallic layers, strengthening
244 the material.^[46] Additionally, the electrospun PA6 mats exhibit excellent fracture toughness

245 performance due to the stress delocalization mechanism in the network of fibers with the work
246 of adhesion between fibers depending on the fiber-fiber contacts.^[47,48]

247 The resistance values of Cu-coated electrospun PA6 fibers were evaluated and
248 correlated with their ability to reduce the triboelectric effect and enhance ESD protection, with
249 a focus on the impact of Cu coating thickness on conductivity, see **Figure 4a-e**. A commercial
250 textile was used as the reference sample, exhibiting a resistance of 411.4 k Ω , while Cu-coated
251 PA6 fibers demonstrated significantly lower resistance. PA6_Cu20 and PA6_Cu25 showed
252 resistances of 53.2 k Ω and 7.9 k Ω , respectively, confirming that increasing Cu thickness
253 enhances conductivity. Pristine PA6 and PA6_Cu15 were beyond the measurement range due
254 to their high resistance, therefore, no resistance data is reported. However, despite its high
255 resistance, PA6 fibers coated with 15nm of Cu still provided adequate ESD protection,
256 indicating that even lower Cu concentrations contribute to dissipating charge. The impact of Cu
257 coating thickness on ESD performance is illustrated in **Figure 4d**, which shows a clear decline
258 in voltage amplitude as the Cu layer thickness increases. Uncoated PA6 fibers exhibit the
259 highest voltage fluctuations, while metallized samples (PA6_Cu15, PA6_Cu20, and
260 PA6_Cu25) show progressively lower peak-to-peak voltage values, demonstrating the
261 effectiveness of the coatings. The quantified peak-to-peak voltage data clearly show that
262 uncoated PA6 fibers display a peak-to-peak voltage of 2.60 ± 0.53 V, while PA6_Cu15,
263 PA6_Cu20, and PA6_Cu25 exhibit significantly lower values of 0.76 ± 0.26 V, 0.49 ± 0.19 V,
264 and 0.37 ± 0.13 V, respectively. These correspond to values 70.9%, 99.5%, and 99.6% lower
265 than the uncoated sample. The reference material achieved a peak-to-peak voltage of $0.25 \pm$
266 0.13 V, corresponding to a value 99.7% lower. As shown in **Figure 4e**, a Cu thickness of at
267 least 20 nm is required to eliminate triboelectric charge buildup. Notably, PA6_Cu20 and
268 PA6_Cu25 achieve values 99.5% and 99.6% lower, respectively, closely approaching the
269 performance of the reference material. The Cu-coated PA6 fibers demonstrated a substantial

270 reduction in electrical resistance and triboelectric charge buildup. This enhanced charge
 271 dissipation can be attributed not only to the metallic conductivity of the deposited Cu layer but
 272 also to the natural formation of copper oxides.^[49–51] These oxides are known to exhibit p-type
 273 semi conductivity due to copper vacancies, which enable effective hole transport and contribute
 274 to static charge dissipation at the fiber–air interface.^[49–51]

275
 276 **Figure 4.** Electrical and triboelectric performance of Cu-coated PA6 fibers. (a–c) Electrical
 277 resistance measurements of a commercial reference textile, PA6_Cu25, and PA6_Cu20,
 278 respectively. (d) Voltage fluctuations over repeated tapping cycles, demonstrating the
 279 progressive reduction in triboelectric charge buildup with increasing Cu thickness. (e) Peak-to-
 280 peak voltage values for each sample, with percentage reductions highlighted in red, confirming
 281 the effectiveness of Cu-coated PA6 fibers in mitigating triboelectric charging.

282 Lastly, to evaluate the durability of the ESD protection in metallized fibers under prolonged
283 mechanical stress, exemplary PA6_Cu20 sample was subjected to 95000 tapping cycles in the
284 triboelectric testing setup, the plot with SEM images are provided in the Supporting Information
285 (**Figure S2**). The triboelectric output remained stable throughout the test, with no significant
286 decline in peak-to-peak voltage, confirming the mechanical robustness and abrasion resistance
287 of the Cu coating under dynamic loading conditions. SEM images taken before and after cycling
288 revealed noticeable structural evolution in the fiber mesh, the fibers became more compacted
289 due to repeated impacts, and localized cracking of the Cu layer was observed. However, these
290 morphological changes did not compromise the electrical performance or ESD protection
291 capability of the fibers in the tested cycle range. Our results are in line with literature as the
292 electrospun Nylon fibers have been previously shown to exhibit high abrasion **resistance**.^[6]
293 Overall, our results underscore the importance of metallization in enhancing both ESD
294 protection and mechanical durability, positioning Cu-coated PA6 fibers as promising
295 candidates for demanding environments requiring sustained electrostatic control and
296 mechanical integrity.

297 **3. Conclusions**

298 This study demonstrates the effectiveness of Cu metallization via PVD in enhancing the
299 ESD protection of electrospun PA6 fiber nonwovens while preserving their structural integrity,
300 breathability, and mechanical properties. The Cu metallization process resulted in a controlled
301 increase in fiber diameter without causing deformation or compromising fiber uniformity. EDS
302 confirmed the successful and homogeneous Cu coating, while FTIR spectroscopy confirmed
303 the presence of copper oxides on the fiber surface. These oxides contribute to charge dissipation
304 through their p-type semiconducting behavior. Metallization modified the surface properties of
305 PA6 fibers, progressively increasing hydrophilicity with increasing Cu thickness. Despite a
306 slight reduction in WVTR, all Cu-coated PA6 fibers remained within the range of highly

307 breathable materials, making them suitable for wearable protective textiles in sensitive
308 environments such as cleanrooms, electronics manufacturing, and healthcare. Cu-coated PA6
309 fibers significantly enhanced mechanical strength and toughness, with a 86.9% increase in
310 tensile stress and an 82.6% improvement in toughness for PA6_Cu25 compared to pristine PA6.
311 These improvements are attributed to forming a polymer–metal nanocomposite interface, which
312 enhances load distribution and material durability. The Cu-coated PA6 fibers demonstrated a
313 substantial reduction in electrical resistance and triboelectric charge buildup. PA6_Cu20 and
314 PA6_Cu25 achieved a peak-to-peak voltage over 99.5% lower compared to pristine PA6,
315 matching commercial ESD materials, confirming their high effectiveness in charge dissipation.
316 A minimum Cu thickness of 20 nm was necessary to achieve optimal conductivity and ESD
317 performance while adhesion remained strong, ensuring long-term durability. This work
318 highlights the potential of Cu-metallized electrospun PA6 fibers as a promising solution for
319 next-generation ESD protection. Compared to conventional ESD materials, these fiber meshes
320 offer a unique combination of lightweight flexibility, breathability, and mechanical strength.
321 The ability to tune Cu layer thickness further enables customization of electrical and mechanical
322 properties, making them highly adaptable for various industrial and wearable applications
323 requiring reliable electrostatic protection.

324 **4. Experimental Section**

325 A PA6 solution was prepared by dissolving PA6 at a concentration of 12% in a 1:1
326 volume ratio mixture of formic acid and acetic acid. The solution was stirred at a constant rate
327 of 400 rpm and a temperature of 25 °C. Electrospinning was conducted using an EC-DIG
328 electrospinner with a climate control system (IME, The Netherlands). The process was carried
329 out for 3 h with a flow rate of 0.1 mLh⁻¹. The needle was set to 14 kV and the collector to -2
330 kV (resulting in a total applied voltage of 16 kV), with a distance of 15 cm between the needle
331 and the collector. The relative humidity was maintained at 40% at 25 °C throughout the process.

332 The metallization process was performed using on demand developed PVD sputtering
333 system (PREVAC sp. z o. o., Poland) under the following parameters. The starting pressure of
334 the chamber was reduced to 3.4×10^{-6} mbar. During the deposition process, Ar gas with a purity
335 of 99.9999% was introduced into the chamber at a flow rate of 100 sccm, reaching a process
336 pressure of 7.57×10^{-3} mbar. The sputtering was performed with a 2-inch diameter Cu target
337 (99.95% purity), using a DC forward power of 15 W at ambient temperature (approximately
338 20°C). The coating thickness was regulated by adjusting the deposition time to 450, 600, and
339 750 s, corresponding to Cu layer thicknesses of 15, 20, and 25 nm, respectively.

340 The SEM investigation used a Zeiss Merlin Gemini II SEM (Zeiss, Germany) with an
341 accelerating voltage of 3 kV and 150 pA current at a 6 mm working distance. Before imaging,
342 pristine PA6 fibers were coated with an 8 nm Au layer deposited on the samples using a rotary
343 pump sputter coater (Q150RS, Quorum Technologies, UK). The Cu coated samples were
344 imaged as prepared from the PVD process. Fiber diameter and pore size distribution were
345 quantified using ImageJ software (v1.53k, NIH, USA). For each sample, 100 individual fiber
346 diameters were measured from SEM micrographs at consistent magnification to ensure
347 comparability. To determine pore size distribution, binarized images of the fibrous mats were
348 analyzed using the *Analyze Particles* function. For each sample, over 250 pores were analyzed
349 to ensure enough measurements for statistical calculations. Elemental mapping was performed
350 using energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy within Zeiss Merlin Gemini II microscope (Zeiss,
351 Germany) to evaluate the effectiveness of Cu deposition on the fibers. Samples were analyzed
352 with Cu coatings of varying thicknesses (15–25 nm). Pure PA6 fibers were coated with a
353 conductive carbon layer using a carbon evaporator (K950, Emitech, UK) to ensure accurate
354 measurements. The mapping was conducted for 300 s at 10 kV, 1 nA, with a working distance
355 of 5.5 mm.

356 Advancing contact angle measurements on pristine and metalized fibers were carried
357 out by placing 3 μL deionized water droplets onto their surfaces. The experiments were
358 conducted at 21°C and 50% RH. Immediately after depositing the liquid, images of the droplets
359 were captured using a camera equipped with an EF-S 60mm f/2.8 Macro USM zoom lens (EOS
360 700D, Canon, Japan). The advancing contact angles were then analyzed using ImageJ software.

361 ATR-FTIR spectroscopy was conducted using a Nicolet iS5 spectrometer (Thermo
362 Fisher Scientific, USA) with a diamond crystal. The spectra were collected over a range of 4000
363 to 400 cm^{-1} , with each spectrum obtained by averaging 32 scans at a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . Post-
364 processing and analysis of the spectra were performed using Origin Pro (2025, OriginLab,
365 USA).

366 The WVTR test was utilized for all samples. In the experimental setup, beakers were
367 filled with 5 mL of deionized water (HydroLab, Poland), and the electrospun meshes were
368 securely placed on top. The beakers with meshes were weighed (VWR, Poland) before
369 immersion in a water bath kept at 37 °C for 24 h with RH less than 30%. After the experiment,
370 all samples were weighed again to measure the water loss. The calculation of WVTR was based
371 on the water loss and the area of the mesh. The average WVTRs and standard error were derived
372 from three measurements per sample type. Electrospun samples were compared with the
373 commercial textile.

374 For mechanical properties analysis, PA6 mats were directly cut into 7 × 4.5 mm
375 rectangular mats. These mats were later used in a tensile testing module (20 N load cell,
376 Kammrath & Weiss, Germany) with an extension rate of 25 μms^{-1} . Stress values were calculated
377 by dividing the force measured by the tensile module by the initial cross-sectional area of the
378 electrospun fiber mat. The average values for maximum stress, toughness, and strain at
379 maximum stress were determined from three separate tests. The thickness of the mats was
380 measured by a digital thickness gauge (TMG-1-T, Checkline Europe B.V, Netherlands). The

381 average values for maximum stress (σ_{\max}) and toughness (W) were calculated from 3 separate
382 measurements using the integrate function in Origin Pro (2025, OriginLab, USA). The repeats
383 are presented in **Figure S3** of the Supporting Information.

384 The resistance measurements were carried out in a 4 contact geometry. Electrode stripes
385 were spaced by a 3.5 mm wide gap, and the studied samples were prepared in the form of 40
386 mm squares. The current was sourced to outer electrodes while the voltage was detected on the
387 inner ones. The current was provided by a programmable Source Meter Unit (Keithley 2400,
388 USA) current source, and the voltage was measured by a multimeter (Keithley 2000, USA).
389 The resistance of the samples was determined based on the linear section of the I-V curve.

390 A bespoke testing setup, designed based on an established measurement standard, was
391 utilized to evaluate the triboelectric properties of Cu-coated PA6 fibers against an Al
392 electrode.^[4] The tapping parameters were set to 1.5 Hz frequency and 20 N force, with a 20 mm
393 separation between the Al counter-electrode and the fiber samples. Due to PA6's relative
394 position in the triboelectric series and its ability to interact effectively with Al, the Cu-coated
395 PA6 fibers were tested against the Al counter-electrode. The fibers were connected to the Al
396 counter-electrode to ensure reliable electrical contact using adhesive carbon disks (Micro to
397 Nano, Netherlands). The electrical output, specifically the voltage generated by the triboelectric
398 interactions, was recorded using a multimeter (Keithley DMM6500, USA). Each sample was
399 measured after a 30-min stabilization period to achieve a steady and clear electrical signal. The
400 output was analyzed in Origin Pro (2025, OriginLab, USA) by assessing the peak-to-peak
401 distance. Each reported value represents the average result from 5000 cycles conducted on each
402 sample type. To assess the long-term mechanical durability of the Cu coating, an exemplary
403 PA6_Cu20 sample underwent 95000 tapping cycles under a force of 20 N and a frequency of
404 1.5 Hz. The triboelectric output was continuously monitored throughout the test to evaluate

405 performance retention. During all measurements, the average RH was maintained at 50%, and
406 the temperature was kept at 23°C.

407 All quantitative data were presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). WVTR values,
408 mechanical properties (maximum stress, toughness), and triboelectric voltage outputs were
409 calculated from a minimum of three independent measurements ($n = 3$), unless stated otherwise.
410 Significance of differences between groups was evaluated using one-way analysis of variance
411 (ANOVA), followed by post hoc t-tests where appropriate. A significance level of 0.05 was
412 used throughout the study. Statistical analysis was carried out using Origin Pro (2025,
413 OriginLab, USA) software.

414

415 **Supporting Information**

416 Supporting information is available as a separate file.

417

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429

430 **Conflict of Interest**

431 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

432

433 **Data Availability Statement**

434 Data related to this study, including raw data and analysis files, are available from the
435 corresponding author upon reasonable request.

436

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